

The Brooklyn-based housing complex, [Fieldbridge Associates LLC](#), has been operating for 32 years, primarily in the Apartment Building Operators business / industry within the Real Estate sector. At this single location, the organization has approximately 60 employees.

Ebbets Field Apartments, an H-Shaped housing complex, was built by the Fieldbridge Associates LLC in the 1960's. This housing complex is located on the western edge of Brooklyn's Crown Heights neighborhood on the former site of Ebbets Field. Ebbets Field Apartments has large studios, along with 1, 2 & 3 Bedroom apartments. Almost all of the units have balcony. The units located on the west side of the building have views of Prospect Park, the statue of liberty and the Manhattan skyline.

The main focus of the Fieldbridge Associates LLC [organization](#) is to provide all residents with high standards of service, 24 hour security, and onsite maintenance and porter staff. The onsite amenities include children's playgrounds, onsite parking garages and state of the art laundry rooms.